

Fabrication of Porous Alumina Using a Natural Foaming Agent

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Abstract

Porous Alumina was prepared by foaming method using shikakai as natural foaming agent (1). The slurry was gel cast in a plastic moulds. The role of different binders and drying control additives on the porosity development were investigated. Optimization of different process parameters (solid loading, shikakai content and drying temperature) indicated a range of parameters for obtaining strong and porous samples. The nature of the mould influenced the defect in the green cast. It is observed that a flexible and thinner mould was best suited for casting. It is proposed that during the setting of the cast, shape change leads to strain generation and thin wall flexible moulds are the best for obtaining a defect free cast. For every solid loading, an optimum shikakai content is required for obtaining a defect free porous cast. The microstructural features also supported this observation. At higher solid loading, less porous cast was obtained.

Keywords: Alumina, Drying temperature, Drying condition, Moulds, Drainage

References:

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